

Condensation Products of Dehydroacetic Acid with Some Aromatic Amines

D. B. Gupta and R. S. Gupta

α - γ -Diacetylacetoacetic acid (I) enolises to its δ -lactone, dehydroacetic acid' (II). The hydrogen atom at C₃ is, however, labile due to adjacent carbonyl groups; the lactone (II) therefore exists in solution as a virtually enolised species^{1,2} (III).

[R = PhN, *o*-ToIN, *p*-ToIN, *m*-ClC₆H₄N, *p*-ClC₆H₄N, *m*-MeOC₆H₄N, α -C₁₀H₇N, β -C₁₀H₇N]

Thus in solution, the acid (II) has only two carbonyl groups. The $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 2 position, however, does not exhibit ketonic reactions due to lactonisation. It is only the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ at C₃ which is responsible for the ketonic behaviour.

Iguchi *et al.*⁴ have studied the condensation products of dehydroacetic acid with a number of amino-acids and compounds, such as H₂NC₆H₄COOH; H₂NC₆H₄SO₂NH₂, H₂NC₆H₄SO₂NHAc, H₂NSO₂C₆H₄CH₂NH₂, and have shown that the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ at C₃

1. Roesweiler and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2758.

2. Berson, *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 5172.

3. Iguchi *et al.*, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1959, 7, 323; 1960, 8, 1; *Yas. Zasshi*, 1957, 77, 1258.

4. *Ibid.*, 1959, 7, 323.

condenses with the amino groups of the above compounds. It was considered worthwhile to extend their work and study the condensation products of dehydroacetic acid with some aromatic amines.

Procedure.—Dehydroacetic acid was prepared from ethyl acetoacetate according to Arndt's³ method. Dehydroacetic acid (0.01M), aromatic amines (0.01M), and ethanol (2Cml) were refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. The reaction mixtures on cooling provided solid products which were recrystallised from ethanol. The condensation products of dehydroacetic acid with aniline, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine, *m*-chloroaniline, *p*-chloroaniline, *m*-anisidine, α -naphthylamine, β -naphthylamine, *p*-nitroaniline, and 2,4,6-tribromoaniline and their characteristics are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

S.No.	Amine.	Products,	Colour.	M.P.	%Yield.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	PhNH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	Cream yellow	118°	50	5.20	5.76
2	<i>o</i> -TolNH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	..	165°	55	5.10	5.44
3	<i>p</i> -TolNH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	..	155°	58	5.15	5.44
4	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	..	118°	50	4.80	5.04
5	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	..	140°	52	4.82	5.04
6	<i>m</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	..	145°	59.5	4.95	5.12
7	α -C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	..	168°	50	4.51	4.78
8	β -C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	..	163°	52	4.51	4.78
9	<i>p</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂	..	..	..	..	..	..
10	2,4,6-Br ₃ C ₆ H ₂ NH ₂	..	..	..	..	..	..

Dehydroacetic acid has been found to react only with the compounds 1—8; it fails to react with 9 and 10 even when the reaction mixtures are refluxed for 10-12 hr. *p*-Nitroaniline (9) does not possibly react due to extremely weak basic character of the -NH₂ group. 2,4,6-Tribromoaniline (10) probably does not react due to steric hindrance caused by two bulky bromine atoms on either side of the -NH₂ group.

All the above condensation products show a positive test with ferric chloride, indicating thereby the presence of a $\gt$ C-OH group. These, however, fail to respond to ketonic reagents. The $\gt$ C=O group at C₂ must have therefore reacted with the -NH₂ group. Hence the possible structure for the above condensation products may be assigned as (IV).

The authors are thankful to Dr. W. U. Malik for providing the laboratory facilities and to Dr. S. S. Joshi for his suggestions.